

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>TID Effect studies for advanced calorimeter detector systems at the high intensity photon irradiation site at gELBE (TIDE@gELBE)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA09-311
General application	<i>Particle physics</i>
Type of test	<i>TID</i>
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Date(s) of the experiment	<i>23-24 October 2023 + 1-2 February 2024</i>
Facility	<i>HZDR-gELBE</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>60 h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

Future calorimetry systems for high-energy physics, such as the upgraded Mu2e-II experiment at Fermilab, face significant challenges due to harsh radiation environments and high intensities.

The radiation exposure on the detectors will see a challenging ten-fold increase and the electromagnetic calorimeter system, which is at present composed of CsI crystals with a new generation of UV extended SiPMs readout, will be exposed to a O(10 kGy) ionization dose, thus degrading its performances under these conditions and it must be replaced with more radiation-resistant materials, alongside robust electronics. A range of scintillating materials, including BaF₂, LYSO, and LaBr₃, are being evaluated with customized SiPMs at HZDR's gELBE beamline, a high-intensity photon irradiation site. These materials are tested for their performance under extreme conditions, with Total Ionizing Dose (TID) studies conducted to assess light yield, energy resolution, and radiation hardness.

BaF₂ emerges as a promising option due to its high radiation resistance and rapid signal generation, though its slow component poses challenges. Alternatives like PbF₂ offer Cherenkov-based light emission but at reduced intensity. Expensive high-performance crystals like LYSO and LaBr₃ are considered for critical inner regions exposed to maximum radiation. The experimental campaign integrates FLUKA simulations to optimize sample irradiation and uses CERN-provided glass dosimeters for precise dose characterization.

This work, supported by the RADNEXT program, aimed to guide the R&D efforts for the Mu2e-II calorimeter while also offering broader potential benefits for industrial and medical applications. Following irradiation and annealing, post-exposure measurements validate the materials' suitability for high-radiation environments.

The total time of the irradiation was ~60h in total separated into two days in October 2023 and two days in February 2024.

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Experiment test report

The gELBE beamline's high-intensity photon irradiation site reported in Figure 1 is highly suited for TID studies. After generating bremsstrahlung radiation for gELBE, the remaining electron beam is deflected by a dipole magnet, passes through a beryllium vacuum window, and is absorbed in a graphite beam dump. Despite this, the photon field behind the dump remains intense, with fluxes ranging from 5×10^{-5} to $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ } \mu\text{cm}^{-2}$ per primary 20 MeV electron. In the narrow plug area beyond the dump, photon fluxes increase by up to two orders of magnitude compared to the direct gELBE beamline, enabling effective high-intensity irradiation.

Figure 1: Left - setup of the photoactivation site. Right - Sketch of the beam dump

This setup has been modelled with FLUKA simulations and will be thoroughly characterized in this campaign using CERN-supplied glass dosimeters.

At the moment of the irradiation three different crystals were tested (1 BaF_2 , 1 LYSO and 3 LaBr_3). In Table 1 the dimensions of the different samples are reported.

Table 1: Dimensions of the tested crystals

Crystal	Dimensions
BaF_2	$3 \times 3 \times 2 \times 14 \text{ cm}^3$
LYSO	$2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 9.8 \text{ cm}^3$
LaBr_3	$2.54 \text{ cm crystal} + 0.5 \text{ cm light guide} + \text{housing } 0.05 \text{ cm Al; } d = 2.54 \text{ cm}$

Each irradiated crystal was paired with a glass TLD dosimeter, positioned near the center of the crystal, as illustrated in Figure 2 (Left). To ensure the crystals were exposed to the intended dose rate, their placement in the experimental area was guided by FLUKA simulations. However, shortly after irradiation commenced, it became apparent that the Monte Carlo simulations had underestimated the dose rate by approximately a factor of 15. Consequently, the crystals were repositioned to an area with a higher dose rate, though the precise value of this rate was not directly controlled. A posteriori, the simulation was re-run accounting for the results obtained from the TLD dosimeter. The rectangular shapes on the right side of Figure 2 (Right) represent the position of the samples.

Figure 2: Left - BaF₂ crystal with glass TLD dosimeter in the irradiation site. Right - final FLUKA simulation of the experimental area.

To evaluate the radiation resistance of the BaF₂ crystal, the light yield (LY) was measured both before and after the irradiation campaign. A low-intensity, collimated ²²Na source, placed between the crystal and a small tagging system consisting of a 3x3x10 mm³ LYSO crystal readout by a 3x3 mm² SiPM, irradiated the crystal in a few mm² region, emitting 511 keV electron-positron annihilation photons. One of the two back-to-back photons was tagged by the LYSO monitor, while the other photon was used to calibrate the crystal under test, which was read out by a 2" UV-extended photomultiplier.

Unfortunately during the irradiation the BaF₂ crystal was broken accidentally and it was impossible to test the characteristics afterwards. The results from LYSO are reported in Figure 3. The integrated dose measured from the TDL dosimeter is ~ 5 kGy, however, the results of the simulation, reported in Figure 2 (Right), show a not homogenous dose along the LYSO crystal, with value peaking at 100 kGy/h. This dose rate dis-uniformity along the crystal axis could explain the unexpectedly high deterioration of the LY compared to the literature.

Figure 3: Charge distribution before and after the irradiation of the LYSO sample

The test on the LaBr₃ samples were performed by LUXIUM®. The table below summarizes the performance of three LaBr₃ crystal samples before and after the irradiation.

Table 2: Performance of the LaBr₃ before and after the irradiation

Sample	Date	PHR @ 662 keV (%)	HT (V)
#1	16/10/2023	3.32	837
#2	16/10/2023	4.21	945
#3	16/10/2023	3.32	848
#1	26/07/2024	4.58	968
#2	26/07/2024	4.37	986
#3	26/07/2024	3.45	892
Sample	Δ PHR @ 662 keV (%)	Δ HT (V)	Δ LO (%)
#1	-1.26	-131	-53
#2	-0.16	-41	-20
#3	-0.13	-44	-23

Sample #1 received the highest integrated dose. The results align with findings reported in the literature. The observed increase in PHR across all samples indicates a deterioration in energy resolution. The elevated HT values required after irradiation suggest a decline in crystal quality, requiring higher voltage to sustain performance. Additionally, the significant reduction in light output across all samples highlights a decrease in the efficiency of converting radiation into a light signal.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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